

Strategic Resource Allocation and Operational Efficiency of Micro-Enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar

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strategic resource allocation, operational efficiency, micro-enterprises, tangible and intangible resources.

Abstract. This study examined the strategic resource allocation and operational efficiency of micro-enterprises, particularly sari-sari store in Guiuan, Eastern Samar, Philippines. Guiuan has various economic conditions and businesses making it a worthy site for studying how efficient micro-enterprises perform. Specifically, it determine the relationship between strategic resource allocation in terms of tangible and intangible resources and operational efficiency. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed. It's objective is to present an accurate of what currently prevails in terms of condition, behavior, and nature of micro-enterprises in the community, focusing on sari-sari store business. A structured survey questionnaire was administered to 84 out of 108 micro-enterprise owners (78% participation rate) in the area. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and person's correlation coefficient. Findings revealed a strong positive and highly significant relationship between strategic resource allocation and operational efficiency ($r = 0.848$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that enterprises allocating resources more strategically tend to demonstrate higher operational efficiency. Results further suggest that micro-enterprises may benefit from enhanced skills development, innovation, and improved access to training program. This study offered valuable insights into how micro-enterprises manage their stores, particularly in community. It highlighted how resources allocated and managed business operations, benefiting micro-enterprise owners and providing great opportunities for others. Ultimately, it contributed to a stable and progressive local economy, where micro-enterprises played a significant role. The study concludes that strengthened resource management practices, developed skills, supported by local government initiatives, can promote sustainable growth and improved operational performance among micro-enterprises.

Introduction

Sari-sari stores are the ones catering to this need with flexible pricing and the tingi system. Through this system, consumers can buy products in small quantities that are compatible with their budgets (Primer Media Inc., 2016). Montiel, (2023) mentioned that this micro-selling scheme enables sari-sari stores to remain operational amidst inflation and economic pressures. Neighborhood stores or sari-sari stores, according to the definition provided, are small-scale businesses that are generally the result of the initiative of a family or a single person and are operated from their homes. Micro-enterprises are businesses that have less than ten employees and the Department of Trade and Industry

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(2021) defines the owned assets of such businesses to be less than ₱3 million. The study was conducted in Guiuan, Eastern Samar, involving 108 registered sari-sari stores classified as micro-enterprises. As a rural area, Guiuan faces a variety of economic and environmental challenges that affect how micro-enterprises use their limited resources. Considering that 89.53% of registered businesses in the Philippines are MSMEs (DTI, 2022), the findings of this study can be serves as a source of knowledge for the government to devise policies and plan programs to support the grassroots level.

Micro-enterprises have shown resistance by their clever adjustment. Shop owners varied their products, started using e-wallets and digital payments, and gave credit to customers in order to retain them. However, there is a scarcity of empirical research which exposes definite resource and operational strategies that these businesses have employed. As a matter of fact, Tobias (2025) has acknowledged that it is very important to uncover such operational patterns and strategic choices which empower micro-enterprises to prevail in tough and volatile market situations.

The study identified a research gap in the limited literature focusing on the challenges, responses, and strategies employed by micro-enterprise owners to improve their business operations. In addition, the study explored the strategic resource allocation and operational efficiency of micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar; specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the strategic resource allocation of micro-enterprises in terms of:
 - 1.1. tangible resources ; and,
 - 1.2. intangible resources?
2. What is the level of operational efficiency of micro-enterprises?
3. Is there a significant relationship between strategic resource allocation and operational efficiency?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design in identifying how micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar distributed their resources and how they perform effectively and efficiently. It's objective is to present an accurate of what currently prevails in terms of condition, behavior, and nature of micro-enterprises in the community, focusing on sari-sari store business. In collecting instrument, structured survey questionnaire served as the main data. The survey questionnaire had 20 questions with different formats including Likert-scale items (range from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree") for capturing efficiently what interviewees believe as well as experience. This method allows for flexibility in measuring strategic pattern as well as level of efficiency among selected sari-sari store owners.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Guiuan, Eastern Samar, a first-class municipality in Eastern Visayas region of the Philippines, with a total of 108 sari-sari store owners through BPLO data. Guiuan has various economic conditions and businesses making it a worthy site for studying how efficient micro-enterprises perform. Guiuan Eastern Samar worthy location for studying how efficient micro-enterprises perform because of its various economic situation as well as businesses.

Respondents of the Study

In collecting data from sari-sari store owners in Guiuan, Eastern Samar, complete enumeration was intended to employed by the researchers. There were a total of 108 sari-sari store owners, but only 84 of respondents (about 78% of the total) cooperated in this survey since some refused to cooperate. Although the population frame included all registered micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar, the partial participation indicates it did not represent a full census. Therefore, eliminating sampling bias and significantly enhancing the reliability and generalizability of the study's findings (Bhandari, 2023). Researchers acquire this information about populations of sari-sari store owners by getting a formal letter from the Business Permit License Office in Guiuan, Eastern Samar. Only registered micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar.

Instrumentation

A survey questionnaire was utilized to collect data developed by Jawed, I., & Siddiqui, D. A. (2019), What matters for firms' performance: Capabilities, Tangible or Intangible Resources, and Chetty, S. R., & Govender, K. K. (2024), Operational efficiency and small and medium enterprise growth in South Africa. The questionnaires had two elements: (1) gathered data on strategic pattern of micro-enterprises' resource allocation, including tangible as well as intangible resources (2) specific assessment of level of micro-enterprises' operational efficiency, including withstanding disruptions in a country's

economy, recovering from disappointments, as well as maintaining long-term development. Respondents selected thoroughly the best choices that matches their circumstances, in ensuring accurate responses. Lastly, the questionnaires were designed to be easy to comprehend and straightforward, reducing the potential biases as it increased the credibility of the responses.

Data Gathering Procedure

Structured approach was used in ensuring a organized data collection process. The researchers asked for permission from the chosen business enterprise; permission was communicated in writing and described the purpose of the research and the potential implications of their participation. The researchers also received approval from the university authority to conduct research. The questionnaires has specific instructions for the participants to follow which encouraged thoughtful, accurate responses.

To avoid reduce missing or incomplete responses, the participants completed them at the same time. Opportunities were provided to seek clarification which established reliability of data in collecting the questionnaires. This structured and systematic process established credibility and comprehensive accuracy for data collection.

Data Analysis

In summarizing demographic characteristics and strategic resource allocation and operational efficiency variables, descriptive statistics were used including frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Pearson's correlation was employed in analyzing the relationships between variables, it's used to identify strength and direction of linear associations, while representing appropriate characteristics of the target population particularly related to strategic resource allocation patterns and operational efficiency levels. This approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting micro-enterprise resilience and supports accurate, reliable conclusions.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Strategic Resource Allocation in terms of Tangible Resources

Statements	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
The money I get from (loans, savings group, or other sources) is very important for how well my micro-enterprise does.	4.04	1.02	Agree	High Level of Influence
I use my extra money (if I have any) to invest in my store, which affects how my micro-enterprise works and grows.	3.96	0.84	Agree	High Level of Influence
The tools I have (like a calculator, weighing scale, or refrigerator) help me run my micro-enterprise efficiently.	3.93	0.90	Agree	High Level of Influence
Keeping enough stocks (like drinks, snacks, and other goods) directly affects how well my micro-enterprise does overall.	4.07	0.77	Agree	High Level of Influence
The store space I have, even if it's just a small part of my house, helps my micro-enterprise run well.	4.19	0.76	Agree	High Level of Influence
Grand Mean	4.04	0.86	Agree	High Level of Influence

Table 1. Level of Strategic Resource Allocation in terms of Tangible Resource

The Level of Strategic Resource Allocation in terms of Tangible Resources got the total grand mean score of 4.04 (SD=0.86), falling under the "Agree" category and interpreted as High Level of Influence. This means that Micro-Enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar were highly influenced in terms of Tangible Resources. Highly influenced micro-enterprises in terms of tangible resources have a substantial impact to its success.

The standard deviation of 0.86 shows a moderate level of variability in responses, indicating that most respondents perceive a high influence of tangible resources, some variation in experience or access to such resources exists to different

enterprises. Thus, this variability may reflect differences in capital, tool or equipment, space, inventory, infrastructure, and other tangible assets among different micro-enterprises. Additionally, to support the idea, tangible resources provide strategic role as resources that serve as the foundation for operational activities and improves enterprise productivity (Samsiah et al., 2025, and Kimani et al., 2024).

Within this Indicator, the statement which got the highest grand mean score of 4.19 (SD=0.768), falling under “Agree” category and interpreted as High Level of Influence was the statement " The store space I have, even if it’s just a small part of my house, helps my micro-enterprise run well". This means that micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar, were highly influenced such factors in shaping their enterprise’ success. This indicator shows how availability of well-maintained facilities not only enhances productivity but also provides a more stable foundation for business growth, reflecting how tangible resources contribute to overall enterprise performance, which results to improve its operational efficiency. Based on the study of (Handoyo et al. 2023), revealed the significant impact of internal factors and external factors, especially the ownership structure that influence the overall performance of the enterprise.

Moreover, the statement "The tools I have (like a calculator, weighing scale, or refrigerator) help me run my micro-enterprise efficiently", received the lowest grand mean score of 3.93 (SD=0.902), falling under the “Agree” category and interpreted as High level of Influence. This indicator emphasize that the respondents understand that machinery, tools, and other physical assets contributing less compared to other factors in the efficiency and productivity of micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar. However, these factors are very essential not only in achieving the long-term goals but also to sustain the competitive advantage of micro-enterprise. Efficient resource utilization is key to improving performance (Dalwai and Salehi, 2021), leading to lower costs, higher margins, and profitability (Derouiche, et al., 2020)

Level of Strategic Resource Allocation in terms of Intangible Resource

Statements	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
I treat my helpers very well (if I have any), and we shared our values (being friendly and honest), which are very crucial for my micro-enterprise.	4.06	1.02	Agree	High Level of Influence
I gave my helpers bonuses and teach them how good they work and how to manage my micro-enterprise.	3.90	0.86	Agree	High Level of Influence
Being recognized for having good customer service is very important for keeping my customers satisfied and making my micro-enterprise grow.	4.30	0.83	Strongly Agree	Very High Level of Influence
I protect my store’s name and the products I sell.	3.64	1.00	Agree	High Level of Influence
I make sure that my products I sell are fresh and not expired.	4.37	0.82	Strongly Agree	Very High Level of Influence
Grand Mean	4.05	0.91	Agree	High Level of Influence

Table 2. Level of Strategic Resource Allocation in terms of Intangible Resources

Based from the data gathered, Level of Strategic Resource Allocation in terms of Intangible Resource obtained the total grand mean score of 4.05 (SD=0.91), falling under the “Agree” category and interpreted as high level of influence. This suggested that Intangible Resources play a significant role in the success of micro-enterprises. This means that micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar were highly influenced in terms of intangible resources.

The standard deviation of 0.91 shows a moderate level of variation in responses, indicating that most of the respondents agree on the significance of intangible resources, there were distinction in the scope to which micro-enterprise’s owners benefited from or having these resources. Based on the studies conducted by Ferdaous & Samsiah et al., (2025), and Zelalem et al., (2022), which suggested that intangible assets play a significant role in financial performance of a business.

Based on the data, the statement which obtained the highest grand mean score of 4.37 (SD=0.818), still falling under the “Agree” category and interpreted as Very High Level of Influence was the statement "I make sure that my products I sell are fresh and not expired". This suggest that micro enterprise owners maintain quality and reliability of products and services to gain competitive edge against competitors as well as customer retention. The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction are generally accepted as major determinants of purchase intention. These concepts play a crucial

role in helping businesses achieve long-term competitive advantage and foster customer loyalty (Limna et al., & Kraiwanit et al., 2022).

Moreover, the statement "I protect my store's name and the products I sell", obtained the lowest grand mean score of 3.64 (SD=1.002), the same with IR above still falling under the "Agree" category and interpreted as High Level of Influence. This indicator presents that micro-enterprise in Guiuan, Eastern Samar were less influenced compared to the other factors in allocating in terms of intangible resources. Having strong business strategy, high operational efficiency, and ownership structure significantly enhance performance (Handoyo et al., 2023).

Level of Operational Efficiency

Statements	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
I always look for small ways and learn in online or real-life situations to keep my micro-enterprise working well.	4.20	0.94	Agree	High Level of Influence
I avoid wasting goods, ensuring stability, and make things more efficient to keep my micro-enterprise running smoothly.	4.11	0.87	Agree	High Level of Influence
I carefully manage my inventory by storing, ordering, and using goods wisely to avoid expiration, getting damage, and having too much stock.	4.29	0.83	Strongly Agree	Very High Level of Influence
I will buy the trending products so that my customer will be satisfied.	4.17	0.93	Agree	High Level of Influence
I make sure my helpers (if I have any) feel comfortable and treated well.	4.11	0.92	Agree	High Level of Influence
I fairly pay my helpers and give them proper benefits, based on their skills and what they do.	4.01	0.90	Agree	High Level of Influence
I use notebooks and calculators to track my sales and expenses so I can make smart decisions for my sari-sari store.	4.07	0.90	Agree	High Level of Influence
I use technology (phones computers, and other devices) for payment apps like GCash to make my micro-enterprise more efficient.	3.92	0.85	Agree	High Level of Influence
I communicate with my customers and suppliers to address problems and find new ideas for new products and services.	4.21	0.84	Strongly Agree	Very High Level of Influence
I promote my sari-sari store through social media and offer better service to my customers.	4.01	1.00	Agree	High Level of Influence
Grand Mean	4.11	0.90	Agree	High Level of Influence

Table 3. Level of Operational Efficiency

From the data gathered, Level of Operational Efficiency obtained the total grand mean score of 4.11 (SD=0.90), falling under the "Agree" category and interpreted as High Level of Influence. The grand mean score indicates that respondents generally agreed that operational efficiency plays an important role in their business This means that micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar were highly influenced by operational efficiency.

The standard deviation of 0.90 shows a moderate level of variation of responses, indicating that while most respondents agreed on the high level of influence of operational efficiency, there was still some variability in their opinions based on different extent of individual experiences or perceptions. There was a study that shows operational efficiency contributes to better performance in competitive markets (Cho, et al. and Lee et al., 2019).

Based on the data, the statement which obtained the highest grand mean score of 4.29 (SD=0.83), still falling under the Strongly "Agree" category and interpreted as Very High Level of Influence was the statement "I carefully manage my inventory by storing, ordering, and using goods wisely to avoid expiration, getting damage, and having too much stock". This indicated that micro-enterprises were strongly influenced by inventory management in order to avoid excessive stock of resources. Internal management capacities, such as planning, organization, and control, are important factors in achieving operational efficiency (Shang, H. et al., 2020; Aguado, R. et al., 2025)

Moreover, the statement "I use technology (phones computers, and other devices) for payment apps like GCash to make my micro-enterprise more efficient", obtained the lowest grand mean score of 3.92 (SD=0.85), falling under the "Agree"

category and interpreted as High Level of Influence, indicates comparatively less emphasis or effectiveness perceived than to other statements. This suggested for potential room for improvement in influencing technology for automation within micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar. According to Das, S. et. al., (2020), to remain the competitiveness of SMEs they should continuously adapt to digital technology.

Variables	Pearson r	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Strategic Resource Allocation Operational Efficiency	0.848	Strong Correlation	0.000	Reject the Ho	Highly Significant

Table 4. Correlation Analysis

The results showed a very strong positive correlation ($r=.848$, $p<.001$). This means that operational efficiency increases along with the strategic resource allocation. The null hypothesis was rejected because the p-value was 0.05 and it was high statistics significance. As a result, the correlation is regarded as highly important. The relationship between the strategic allocation of resources and the effectiveness of operations was evident and substantial. This suggest that increased operational is directly related to strategic resource allocation.

Conclusion and Implications

Micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar understand the value of both tangible and intangible resources in maintaining their operations, emphasizing the necessity of bolstering both for long-term commercial success. Micro-enterprises have a high operational efficiency level, indicating that they can make good use of their resources to produce goods and services. Businesses that strategically allocate their resources are more likely to achieve better performance, as evidenced by the high correlation between operational efficiency and effective strategic resource allocation. The results also imply that although micro-enterprises operate effectively, they might gain even more by improved abilities, creativity, and training that enabled them to maintain expansion and deal with operational difficulties.

The findings of the study highlighted important insights of the strategic resource allocation of micro-enterprises in terms of tangible resources and was interpreted as a high level of influence. This suggested that tangible resources play a significant role in how micro-enterprises strategically managed and allocated for what was available to them. When looking at intangible resources it was interpreted as a high level of influence. This demonstrates that intangible resources, such as values, cultures, knowledge, skills, and relationships, are regarded by micro-enterprises as equally important in shaping their overall resource allocation strategies. The level of operational efficiency was also measured and was interpreted as a high level of influence. This finding reflected that micro-enterprises view their operational practices as generally efficient, and that such efficiency plays an essential role in sustaining their day-to-day business activities.

The findings of the study revealed a strong positive and highly significant relationship between strategic resource allocation and operational efficiency, indicating that enterprises allocating more strategically tend to demonstrate higher operational efficiency. Results further suggest that micro-enterprises may benefit from enhanced skills development, innovation, and improve access to training program. The study concludes that strengthened resource management practices, developed skills, supported by local government initiatives, can promote sustainable growth and improved operational performance among micro-enterprises.

On a broader scale, the study provides a significant insight into various micro-enterprises, especially in the rural communities, in terms of resource allocation and operations not only benefits business owners, but also creates more opportunities for other individuals, making the local economy more stable and progressive.

There is a significant relationship between strategic resource allocation and operational efficiency of micro-enterprises in Guiuan, Eastern Samar. It indicates that micro-enterprises that allocate their resources more strategically are likely to achieve greater efficiency in their operations.

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Competing Interests Statement

Regarding the publication of this work the author states that they have no conflict of interest and copyright is assigned to the publishing journal.

Data Availability Statement

All information was collected in compliance with ethical research guidelines guaranteeing respondents confidentiality and voluntary participation.

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Appendices

No appendices are included in this article